

Information, Quantum Probability and Reflection/Refraction

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Quantum mechanics is known for its “square root” probability i.e. the existence of a wavefunction $W(x)$ such that $P(x) = W^*(x)W(x)$. This begs the question: Why is this the case? In Maxwell’s electromagnetic theory of the photon, a similar situation arises except that one has energy density instead of $P(x)$ which consists of $.5c^2$ Electric field* Electric field + $.5c^2$ Magnetic field*Magnetic field. The “square root” object is a physical observable (Electric field, Magnetic field) which both behave as $\cos(-Et+px)$ and so, more accessible than $W(x)$.

Alternatively one may use Fermat’s least time principle for light to show that in two dimensional problems (reflection/refraction) d/dx (used in extremization) is really the operator of momentum in that direction i.e. a spatial invariant direction. Thus $A=px$ such that $dA/dx=p = x$ component of momentum which may be generalized to $A=-Et+p \cdot r$. ($p \cdot r$) may be written as $-i \ln(\exp(ip \cdot r))$ with $\exp(ip \cdot r)$ representing a “kind of probability”. This probability may be considered a square root probability because for uniform motion (light) all x points along a ray should have equal probability. Thus $\exp(ip \cdot r)$ maps into a constant which happens if one takes the modulus.

Both of the above approaches (using continuity at x or a kind of conservation of probability and a momentum) may be used to solve the problem of an incident beam of light moving in the positive x direction hitting a medium and both reflecting and refracting. For example see (1). The goal is to find the two intensity values associated with the reflected and refracted beams assuming the incident intensity is known.

In this note, we take a different approach to finding the two unknowns, one that does not use the idea of the electric field proportional to $\cos(-Et+px)$ or the probability $\exp(ipx)$. We wish to solve the problem using only the idea of information and stress the importance of beginning with energy conservation a priori unlike the two approaches listed above.

We postulate that there are two sets of information in this problem. First there is the notion of Energy = $p(\text{momentum in a vacuum}) n / c/n$ where n is the index of refraction. Thus the incident and reflected light are associated with pc_1, c_1 and the refracted with pc_2, c_2 with energy being the same for all. Second there is the idea of conservation of energy i.e. if ten photons with energy E hit the surface and $a/10$ reflect and $(1-a)/10$ refract, then the sum of the refracted and reflected energy equals the initial energy. Energy is then equated with intensity through $\text{Intensity}/c = \text{energy} (1)$.

Using only these two pieces of information we argue one should be able to find the intensity of both the reflected and refracted ray. This leads to an immediate problem because there are two unknowns and only one equation, namely conservation of energy i.e. $I(A)/c_1 = I(B)/c_1 + I(C)/c_2$ where A is the incident beam, B the reflected and C the refracted. Writing as: $I(A)/c_1 - I(B)/c_1 = I(C)/c_2$ (i.e. a spatial instead of time grouping) suggests a possible solution might be to employ a difference of squares noting that $1/c = p/E$ with E being a constant in the problem. Thus one may reduce the problem to $A+B=C$ and $p_1A-p_1B=p_2C$. This is of the form of a new kind of “square root” type probability, but leads to two equations with two unknowns (A is assumed to be known) which allows the problem to be solved.

Continuity of Electric Field

Maxwell in the latter half of the 1800s developed two wave equations from his set of electromagnetic equations, one in the electric field and the other in the magnetic, to describe a photon. Thus phenomena involving light may be analyzed using electromagnetic theory. In particular, following (1), one insists an electric field and its first derivative remain continuous in a problem involving a beam of light with electric field $A \exp(ip_1 x)$ moving in the positive x direction hitting a medium and both reflecting and refracting i.e. producing $B \exp(-i p_1 x)$ and $C \exp(i p_2 x)$. The continuity exists at $x=0$ so this leads to two equations:

$$A+B=C \quad \text{and} \quad p_1 A - p_1 B = p_2 C \quad \text{with} \quad p_1 = pc_1 \quad \text{and} \quad p_2 = pc_2 \quad \text{because} \quad E=pc \quad \text{and} \quad E \text{ is constant} \quad ((1))$$

If A is known, then B and C may be solved in terms of A as done in (1). Thus the problem is completely solved. As a side note, one may show that:

$$AA/c_1 = BB/c_1 + CC/c_2 \quad ((2))$$

which is conservation of energy which must hold. No a priori assumption of conservation of energy was made.

Unusual Probabilities

If one uses Fermat's principle for light to solve a two dimensional reflection or refraction problem with the flat mirror surface along the x axis at $y=b$, this problem may be formulated as $dt_1/dx + dt_2/dx = 0$ with t_1 and t_2 being times of the incident and reflected or refracted rays. dt_1/dx and dt_2/dx , however, are proportional to momentum in the x direction. Thus one has d/x the generator of a spatially invariant variable being linked with momentum in that direction. Thus one may write:

$$A=px \quad \text{and} \quad dA/dx = p \quad \text{and this may be generalized to} \quad A = -Et + p \cdot r \quad ((3))$$

An eigenfunction of $-i d/dx$ is $\exp(-iEt + ip \cdot r)$. This may be treated as a kind of unusual probability and one may use this together with an OR (add) situation to create conservation of probability and momentum equations using only $\exp(ipx)$ i.e. no time. ($\exp(-iEt)$ may be treated separately.) $\exp(ipx)$ groups events which exist in the same spatial region (i.e. the incident and reflected) rays even if they do not exist at the same time i.e. an incident photon hits the surface and becomes either a reflected or a refracted one. In order to remove time from the picture, one may imagine a steady state situation. Then reflected and refracted photons exist in the same region of space while the refracted one exists in another. This is a kind of equilibrium scenario which removes time. Ultimately one has the same two equations as in ((1)), but the reasoning seems to be different. Again conservation of overall energy is not used a priori as a condition, although it must hold.

Information Only

In this note we wish to use only information arguments to solve the reflection/refraction problem. We assume no knowledge of Maxwell's equations and electric and magnetic fields and no knowledge of Fermat's principle and the $\exp(ipx)$ unusual probability form. We assume only the following:

1. $E = p_1 c_1$ where $p_1 = p/n_1$ and $c_1 = c/n_1$ where p and c are vacuum values.

n_1 is the index of refraction and is a critical piece of information which governs refraction.

2. Conservation of energy i.e. if 10 photons are part of the incident beam and three reflect, then seven refract, with the energy of all remaining constant i.e. momentum and c changing in the new medium. Following (1) we write this as: $I(A)/c_1 = I(B)/c_1 + I(C)/c_2$ ((4)) where A is the incident beam, B the reflected and C the refracted. We also note that this conservation law groups by time i.e. the incident beam exists in one region of time and at a later time it becomes reflected and refracted light.

We argue that 1 and 2 should be sufficient information to solve the problem i.e. find the probabilities associated with reflection and refraction assuming a known incident intensity. This, however, seems like a problem because:

3. There is one equation (conservation of energy) and two unknowns i.e. $I(B)$ and $I(C)$ the intensities

3 appears to be a serious problem unless there are in fact two equations which combine to yield conservation of energy. To see such a possibility, consider $E/c = p$ where E is energy which is constant. In such a case, ((4)) becomes:

$$I(A)p_1 - p_1 I(B) = p_2 I(C) \quad ((5))$$

We note that ((5)) now groups in space (instead of time as in ((4))). The LHS of ((5)) is reminiscent of a difference of squares because $I(A)$, $I(B)$ and $I(C)$ must all be positive by definition of intensity. Thus one may break ((5)) into two equations using $I(z) = zz$ or:

$$A+B = C \quad \text{and} \quad p_1 A - p_1 B = p_2 C \quad ((6)) \quad \text{where} \quad p_1 = 1/c_1 \quad \text{and} \quad p_2 = 1/c_2 \quad \text{and} \quad E=1$$

((6)) allows one to solve for B and C in terms of A , but these two equations follow from conservation of energy and so guarantee a priori.

((6)) have the form of a new kind of probability, namely a square root type because $I(z)=zz$. The first equation is a kind of conservation of new probability using a grouping in space (not time). It is as if time has been removed and one only considers space. The second equation (which also removes time) is a kind of conservation of momentum. These two, as noted, solve for B and C and are compatible with conservation of energy a priori.

Conclusion

In conclusion we argue that the traditional continuity of electric field and its first derivative approach to solving a reflection/refraction problem relies on (1) Maxwell's electromagnetic equations and (2) does not impose conservation of energy a priori. In fact as in (1) one may simply solve for the weights of the reflected and refracted electric fields and leave it at that. (Conservation of energy exists, but is an afterthought). Similarly, considering Fermat's principle leading to the existence of an unusual kind of probability $\exp(ipx)$ with no time present and then establishing conservation of probability and momentum using an OR situation with an unusual grouping in space and not time, also does consider conservation of energy a priori and assumes a knowledge of this unusual probability and its form $\exp(ipx)$.

In this note we suggest one start with conservation of energy which must exist i.e. $I(A)/c1 = I(B)/c1 + I(C)/c2$ (as in (1)) with A being the incident beam, B the reflected and C the refracted. There is immediately a major problem in that there are two unknown $I(B)$ and $I(C)$ and one equation. Two equations are necessary. To resolve this issue, we use $E=pc$ to write $1/c$ as $E/c = p$ because E energy is constant and write conservation of energy (a time grouped equation) as a space grouped equation: $I(A)p1 - I(B)p1 = I(C)p2$. This suggests a difference of squares on the LHS with $I(A)=AA$: $A+B = C$ and $p1A - p1B = p2C$. These two equations automatically ensure conservation of energy (because they come from such an equation) yet they also allow one to solve for B and C in terms of A. One needs no information about electromagnetic equations or unusual probabilities $\exp(ipx)$. Furthermore, A,B,C have the form of a new kind of square root probability (in the sense that $I(A) = AA$) based on space and not time. Thus the two equations are a kind of conservation of probability (OR situation) with conservation of momentum with an unusual space instead of time grouping.

References

1. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Reflection_phase_change